

AGENDA

GREENSCENT YOUTH ASSEMBLY IN-PERSON MEETING IN ROME

SEPTEMBER 22-24, 2023

FRIDAY 22ND

CHECK IN - 14.00-16.30

SANTA LUCIA FILIPPINI CASA PER FERIE, LARGO DI SANTA LUCIA
FILIPPINI, 20, 00186 ROMA RM, ITALY

*IF YOU ARRIVE BEFORE 14.00, YOU CAN LEAVE YOUR LUGGAGE AT THE
RECEPTION*

MEETING EACH OTHER - 16.30-17.30

SOCIAL ACTIVITIES, PRESENTATION OF THE PROGRAM
ON THE HOTEL ROOF TERRACE

SNACK BREAK - 17.30-17.45

GETTING STARTED - FARM TO FORK - 17.45-18.30

INTRODUCTION TO FARM TO FORK AND CITIZEN JOURNALISM IN
GREENSCENT

IN THE HOTEL MEETING ROOM

GETTING STARTED - CITIZEN JOURNALISM - 18.30-19.00

INTRODUCTION TO FARM TO FORK AND CITIZEN JOURNALISM IN
GREENSCENT

IN THE HOTEL MEETING ROOM

FRIDAY 22ND

WALK TO THE RESTAURANT - 19.30-20.00

WE WALK TOGETHER TO THE RESTAURANT TAKING A SHORT ROUNDABOUT TO SEE SOME OF THE CITY

DINNER AT ROSSOPOMODORO - 20.00-22.00

LARGO DI TORRE ARGENTINA, 1, 00186 ROMA RM, ITALIEN

WALK TO THE HOTEL- AFTER DINNER

DITTE AND KATHRINE WILL WALK BACK TO THE HOTEL SANTA LUCIA FILIPPINI CASA PER FERIE, LARGO DI SANTA LUCIA FILIPPINI, 20, 00186 ROMA RM, ITALY

MAKE SURE THAT YOU ARE READY FOR TOMORROW'S PROGRAM TOMORROW AT 9.15 (BREAKFAST BETWEEN 8.30 AND 9.15)

SATURDAY 23RD

BREAKFAST IN THE HOTEL - 8.30-9.15

BREAKFAST AND GOOD MORNING SANTA LUCIA FILIPPINI CASA PER FERIE
LARGO DI SANTA LUCIA FILIPPINI, 20, 00186 ROMA RM, ITALY

WALK TO UNINETTUNO - 9.15 - 9.30

WE ARE LEAVING THE HOTEL FOR THE DAY, AND THE FIRST STOP IS UNINETTUNO'S MULTIMEDIA ROOM. WE WILL WALK TOGETHER.

IMPORTANT: REMEMBER TO WEAR PRACTICAL SHOES AND CLOTHES, AND BRING A BOTTLE OF WATER. IT MAY GET VERY HOT DURING THE DAY, SO SUNSCREEN AND A HAT IS A GOOD IDEA.

FARM TO FORK STUDENT INNOVATION - 9.30-10.00

PITCHES FROM OPEN INNOVATION CHALLENGE FINALISTS

UNINETTUNO'S MULTIMEDIA ROOM, PIAZZA GRAZIOLI, 17 - 00186 ROME

WORKSHOP BY SF4C - 10:00-13.00

SF4C - SCHOOL FOOD 4 CHANGE WILL TAKE US THROUGH A WORKSHOP ABOUT THE COMPLEXITY OF THE FOOD SYSTEM.

UNINETTUNO'S MULTIMEDIA ROOM, PIAZZA GRAZIOLI, 17 - 00186 ROME

WALK TO FARMERS MARKET - 13:00-13.30

WE WILL WALK TOGETHER, TALKING ABOUT THE WORKSHOP.

CITIZEN JOURNALISM: FARM TO FORK - 13:30-14.00

WE WILL EXPLORE THE FARMERS MARKET WITH A FOCUS ON THE SUSTAINABILITY OF FOOD PRODUCTS USING THE GREENSCENT APP TO DOCUMENT OUR FINDINGS.

CAMPAGNA AMICA MARKET, VIA DI S. TEODORO, 7400186 ROMA RM

LUNCH AND CITIZEN JOURNALISM - 14:00-15.00

LUNCH AND CONTINUED CITIZEN JOURNALISM AT THE FARMERS MARKET.

SATURDAY 23RD

WALK TO EVOO SCHOOL - 15.00-16.00

WE WILL WALK TOGETHER

VISIT TO EVOO SCHOOL - 15.30-17.30

INTRODUCTION TO BIODIVERSITY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN THE PRODUCTION OF OLIVE OIL, INCLUDING A TASTING.

VIA NAZIONALE, 89/A/10 PIANO, 00184 ROMA RM

TRANSPORT AND CITIZEN JOURNALISM - 17.30-20.00

WE WILL USE PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION AND WALK TOGETHER WHILE USING THE GREENSCENT APP TO DOCUMENT OUR VISITS OF THE DAY AND START WRITING BLOG POSTS FOR THE GREENSCENT WEBSITE AND SO-ME.

DINNER AT COMODO MERCATO TREVÌ - 20.00-22.00

VIA DEL LAVATORE, 88B, 00187 ROMA RM, ITALY

TRANSPORT TO THE HOTEL- AFTER DINNER

DITTE AND KATHRINE WILL WALK BACK TO THE HOTEL SANTA LUCIA FILIPPINI CASA PER FERIE, LARGO DI SANTA LUCIA FILIPPINI, 20, 00186 ROMA RM, ITALY

*MAKE SURE THAT YOU ARE READY FOR TOMORROW'S PROGRAM
TOMORROW AT 9.15 (BREAKFAST BETWEEN 8.30 AND 9.15)*

SUNDAY 24TH

BREAKFAST IN THE HOTEL - 8.15-9.15

GOODMORNING, BREAKFAST AND CHECK OUT AT THE HOTEL

EVERYBODY SHOULD HAVE CHECKED OUT BEFORE THE NEXT SESSION.

*YOU CAN LEAVE YOUR LUGGAGE AT THE RECEPTION UNTIL YOUR DEPARTURE
IMPORTANT: IF YOU HAVE A TIGHT SCHEDULE AFTER THE WORKSHOP, BRING
YOUR LUGGAGE TO UNINETTUNO.*

WALK TO UNINETTUNO - 9.15 - 9.30

COMPETENCE WORKSHOP - 9.30 - 12.00

**DURING THE WORKSHOP, WE WILL BE DISCUSSING AND PROVIDING
FEEDBACK ON THE GREENSCENT COMPETENCE FRAMEWORK.**

UNINETTUNO'S MULTIMEDIA ROOM, PIAZZA GRAZIOLI, 17 - 00186 ROME

SHORT BREAK- 12.00 - 12.15

EVALUATING THE CITIZEN JOURNALISM TOOLS - 12.15-13:00

UNINETTUNO'S MULTIMEDIA ROOM, PIAZZA GRAZIOLI, 17 - 00186 ROME

FOLLOW UP AND FAMILY PHOTO - 13.00-13.15

UNINETTUNO'S MULTIMEDIA ROOM, PIAZZA GRAZIOLI, 17 - 00186 ROME

PIZZA SLICES AT UNINETTUNO - 13.15-14:00

WALK TO THE HOTEL- 14:00 - 14:15

WE WILL WALK BACK TO THE HOTEL TO PICK UP OUR BAGS

GOODBYE AT THE HOTEL - 14:15

WE WILL PICK UP OUR BAGS AT THE HOTEL AND SAY GOODBYE